

Received: 11 June 2021/ Accepted: 25 June 2021/ Published: 30 June 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5047363>

Bioconversion of paddy straw residues into quality biocompost using improved TNAU Biomineralizer

P. Kalaiselvi^{1*}, P. Jayasankaran¹, B.M. Porkavi¹, S. Paul Sebastian², V. Davamani¹, E. Parameswari¹, K. Suganya¹

¹ Department of Environment Sciences, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, 641003, India

² Anbil Dharmalingam Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Trichy, 620027, India

*Corresponding author: P. Kalaiselvi (kalaiselvi.p@tnau.ac.in)

This work was presented at the *Fifth International Conference on Reuse and Recycling of Materials (ICRM-2020)* held during 11-13, December 2020 at Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala, India, 686560

Introduction: Agro biomass includes paddy straw, wheat straw, husk, nutshells, woodchips, bagasse, press cake and others. Agro biomass which consists mainly cellulose (35-50%), hemicelluloses (25-30%) and lignin (25-30%) but compositions differ for different types of biomasses. Rice is the staple food crop in India and huge dry matter is obtained after threshing. For four tonnes of rice grain obtained around 6 tonnes of straw was produced. On an average these residues contain about 0.5% nitrogen, 0.2% phosphorus and 1.5% potassium. Annually, 97.19 Mt of straw is produced, in which around 22.3 Mt remains unutilized. They were burnt by farmers and it emits greenhouse gases, particulate matter and smoke which pollutes the atmosphere (1). If it is recycled in agriculture, totally 6.5 million tonnes of chemical fertilizer consumed per annum can be replaced from the nutrients coming out with this residues, which is roughly account to 30 % of total NPK consumption in the country (2). With this background the present study was carried out to develop a methodology that effectively degrades the lignocellulose biomass with the elite microbial cultures developed in an economically feasible way without causing any deleterious effect to the environment.

Methods: The paddy straw obtained from the TNAU University farm unit was utilized for biocompost production. The paddy straw was shredded and compost heaps were made. Totally there are five treatments and four replications with different combinations, treatments were imposed in the compost heaps.

Results & Discussions: The initial CN ratio of the paddy straw is 64:1. The compost heaps which received the treatment of shredded paddy straw CN (30:1) ratio adjusted with urea + improved TNAU Biomineralizer @ 2 kg t⁻¹ recorded the shortest period of 85 days for biocompost production. The final CN ratio of the biocompost produced is 18:1. Also the biocompost had the high nutrient content of 0.82%, 0.23% and 1.18% of NPK, compared to other treatments.

Conclusions: It can be concluded that, microbial degradation proves to be the safe, cost effective and efficient ecofriendly method in lignocellulose degradation.

Key words: *Agro biomass, Bio compost, TNAU Biomineralizer, Nutrients*

References

1. Ghosh, SK. Biomass and bio-waste supply chain sustainability for bio-energy and bio-fuel production. *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, 2016; 31:31-39.
2. Wang W, Yan L, Cui Z, Gao Y, Wang Y, Jing R. Characterization of a microbial consortium capable of degrading lignocellulose. *Bioresource technol.* 2011;102 (19):9321-9324.

